

**ORGANIATIONAL CHANGE READINESS AND COMPETIVE ADVANTAGE OF
HOSPITALITY FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE.**

BY

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of organisational change readiness and competitive advantage of hospitality firms in Rivers State. The study has organisational change readiness as its predictor variable with individual change readiness and leadership change readiness as dimensions while the criterion variable is competitive advantage with customer satisfaction and cost leadership as its measures. The study adopted a survey design with a population of 141 top level managers drawn across 34 hotels in Port Harcourt. The structure questionnaire was used in collecting data from respondents, we adopted the use of the spearman rank correlation statistical tool in testing the relationship between the dimensions of the predictor variable and the measures of criterion variable..The findings of the study revealed organisational change readiness as a strong predictor of competitive advantage hence we made the following recommendations:. Organizations should encourage individual employees on continuous learning and adaptability, this is because individual employees who are mentally and emotionally ready for change are more likely to embrace innovation, new technologies and evolving business models and thereby enhancing competitive advantage of the firm, leaders in the organisation should build and empower change agents across all levels of the organization through training and mentorship, they themselves should spare head the change process.

Keywords: **Change readiness ,Competitive advantage, Firms, Hospitality Organization,**

INTRODUCTION

The hospitality industry identified as one of the fastest growing sectors in the Nigeria economy and Rivers state in specific. The industry contributes significantly to employment, investment, and economic growth. No doubt, the hospitality industry plays a vital role in supporting business tourism, oil and gas operations, and leisure activities. However, the operative environment of the industry is characterized by intense competition, evolving customer expectations, technological disruptions, and frequent economic and policy changes. To remain competitive, firms must not only respond to these changes but also build internal capabilities that make them ready and adaptable to change.

As globalization, technology, and customer preference continually evolve, rivalry among hospitality firms also heightened, creating the need for hospitality firms to develop unique strategies facilitate their **competitive advantage**. Competitive advantage refers to a firm's ability to deliver superior value to its customers and achieve higher performance than its rivals. According to Porter (1985), competitive advantage arises from the effective implementation of strategies that create value either through cost leadership, differentiation, or focus. In the hospitality context, this advantage may be derived from exceptional service quality, brand reputation, innovative technology adoption, strategic location, skilled workforce, and customer relationship management. Firms that can effectively harness these elements often enjoy increased patronage, customer loyalty, and profitability.

Organizational change readiness on the other hand refers to the extent to which an organization is psychologically and structurally prepared to implement and sustain change successfully (Armenakis and Harris 2021). It involves the willingness of management and employees to accept new ideas, adjust to new technologies, restructure processes, and embrace innovation. A high level of change readiness enables firms to respond quickly to market dynamics, improve

service quality, and leverage new opportunities for growth. Conversely, organizations that resist change often face declining performance, loss of market share, and reduced customer loyalty.

Change readiness has become a critical factor for survival and success. Many firms, however, still rely on traditional management approaches and outdated operational systems, making it difficult to adapt to new technologies, sustainability practices, and evolving consumer behaviors. This situation raises concerns about their ability to maintain a competitive advantage in a constantly changing business landscape.

Understanding how organizational change readiness influences competitive advantage is therefore essential for hospitality firms in Rivers state hence the need for this study, the study can help identify the key change drivers such as leadership readiness and commitment, individual employee involvement, innovation culture, and technological adaptation that enable firms to outperform competitors and achieve competitive advantage over rivals..

Statement of the Problem

In today's ever evolving world with intense competition, uncertainties and high level of hostility characterizing business operative environment, firms within the hospitality industry must continually adapt to changing customer preferences, technological innovations, and market uncertainties. Hospitality firms in Rivers state are constantly faced with stiff rivalry driven by emerging hotels, guest houses, and international brands offering similar services. However, many hospitality firms in the state struggle to sustain a competitive edge due to their limited readiness to embrace and manage organizational change effectively.

Despite the importance of organizational change readiness as a composition of leadership readiness and commitment, individual readiness, employee adaptability, communication systems, and innovation culture as an inevitable culture for achieving competitive advantage, many hospitality firms in Rivers State exhibit resistance to change, outdated operational models, and poor staff engagement in change processes. This lack of readiness often results in slow response to market shifts, low customer satisfaction, and decreased organizational performance.

Worthy to note also, is that issues such as inadequate training, insufficient technological adoption, and weak change management structures does hinder hospitality firms from leveraging opportunities that could strengthen their competitiveness and give them competitive edge over rivals. Consequently, while other regions' hospitality industries evolve rapidly through strategic change initiatives, those in Rivers State risk stagnation and loss of market relevance.

The problem as identified in this study, therefore, lies in understanding the extent to which organizational change readiness can enhance a firm's ability to gain and sustain competitive advantage within the hospitality industry in Rivers State,.

Conceptual Framework of organizational change readiness and competitive advantage

Source: Survey research 2025

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between change readiness and corporate survival of Hospitality firms in Rivers State. However, the specific objectives of the study are stated thus:

- i. To examine the relationship between individual readiness and customer satisfaction of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.
- i. To examine the relationship between individual readiness and cost leadership of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.
- ii. To examine the relationship between leadership readiness and customer satisfaction of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.
- iii. To examine the relationship between leadership readiness and cost leadership of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses will guide the study

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between individual readiness and customer satisfaction of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between individual readiness and cost leadership of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between leadership readiness and customer satisfaction of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between leadership readiness and cost leadership of Hospitality firms in Rivers State.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Organizational change readiness

Organizational Change readiness is generally defined as a state in which organizational units possess the necessary mindset and capabilities to embark on a planned change effort. Armenakis et al. (2021). It is “the beliefs, attitudes, and intentions of organizational members regarding the need for and capability of implementing organizational change.” It reflects both the willingness to change and the perceived ability to manage and succeed in the change effort (Weiner, 2020). It is considered a prerequisite for effective change implementation, acting as both a predictor and a mediator of change outcomes. However, in the global market, organizational change is a critical process in modern management, especially in a dynamic global environment characterized by

digital transformation, evolving market demands, and socio-economic disruptions. With this circumstance, the concept of change readiness has become a pivotal focus in understanding how individuals and organizations prepare for, respond to, and engage in transformation processes (Napier, et al., 2022). Change readiness, as a multidimensional construct, refers to the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral preparedness of stakeholders to accept and implement organizational change (Holt et al., 2020).

Change readiness, as conceptualized by Armenakis and Harris (2021), is not merely a static condition but an idea that can be shaped and influenced through strategic communication. Central to their framework is the thought that readiness for change can be cultivated by delivering a set of targeted messages that address their beliefs, emotions, and expectations. This approach is often referred to as the Five-Message Framework, and it has become a foundational model in organizational change literature. The first component of the framework is discrepancy, which refers to the recognition of a gap between the current state and a desired future state. This message aims to generate an understanding that change is necessary. If employees do not perceive a discrepancy, if they believe that “things are fine the way they are”, they are unlikely to engage with or support the change process. Leaders must therefore clearly articulate why the status quo is no longer sufficient and why change is urgent and justified (Armenakis and Harris, 2022).

The second message is appropriateness, which involves convincing organizational members that the specific change being proposed is the correct course of action to address the identified discrepancy. Even when individuals acknowledge the need for change, they may resist if they believe the solution is flawed or misguided. Thus, this message focuses on aligning the proposed change with organizational goals, values, and evidence of likely success. Appropriateness increases when individuals perceive the change as logical, necessary, and strategically sound.

The third element, efficacy, pertains to individuals’ belief in their own ability or the organization's collective capability to successfully implement the change. This dimension is rooted in Bandura’s (1997) theory of self-efficacy, which emphasizes that belief in one’s competence is essential to motivation and performance. In the change readiness, efficacy involves not only skills and resources but also the emotional confidence that change can be

accomplished. If employees lack this confidence, even a well-conceived change may falter due to inaction or passive resistance.

Principal support, the fourth message, involves trust in and endorsement of the change by key organizational leaders and influencers. Employees tend to look for cues from credible authorities such as supervisors, executives, or respected peers when evaluating whether to support change. When these figures actively champion the change, it signals organizational alignment and reduces uncertainty. Conversely, mixed messages or silence from leaders can undermine credibility and readiness. Finally, valence refers to individuals' perception of the personal benefits or costs associated with the change. This message addresses the question, "What's in it for me?" If employees believe the change will lead to positive outcomes such as increased job satisfaction, opportunities for advancement, or improved work conditions they are more likely to be receptive. On the other hand, if the change is seen as threatening or disadvantageous, resistance is more likely.

Individual change readiness

Individual change readiness refers to the state of preparedness of an individual to successfully adapt to changes, challenges, or new roles within an organization or environment (Adam and Hanafi, 2022). Individual readiness encompasses various factors that contribute to an individual's ability to meet demands effectively. This includes cognitive abilities, emotional intelligence, prior experience, and self-efficacy, all of which play critical roles in how well one can navigate transitions (Al-Maamari, Q. et al., 2021). Moreover, fostering a culture of continuous learning within organizations can enhance individual readiness. Continuous training and development opportunities enable individuals to expand their skills and adapt to evolving roles while also boosting their confidence.

Individual readiness refers to a staff overall preparedness to successfully engage with various processes, technologies, and innovations introduced by the organization. This concept encompasses multiple dimensions that influence how effectively a student can participate in and benefit from the educational process. According to Wagner et al. (1998), individual readiness is

not limited to technical proficiency or access to resources, but also includes attitudinal and cognitive factors that shape learning engagement.

Leadership change Readiness

Leadership change readiness refers to the preparedness of leaders in an organization to assume leadership roles and responsibilities effectively. This concept includes not only the acquisition of necessary skills and knowledge, but also the psychological, emotional, and strategic readiness to lead in diverse and often complex environments. It involves the capacity to make decisions, inspire others, navigate organizational dynamics, and respond adaptively to change. According to McCauley, et al.(2020), leadership change readiness is shaped by a combination of internal and external factors that influence an individual's preparedness to assume leadership roles. Internal factors include a leader's self-awareness, which is the capacity to understand one's emotions, strengths, weaknesses, and the impact of one's behavior on others. This self-awareness is considered foundational to emotional intelligence and is strongly associated with effective leadership (Goleman, Boyatzis, & McKee, 2023). Leaders who possess high self-awareness are better equipped to make informed decisions, adapt to changing circumstances, and maintain productive interpersonal relationships.

Another crucial internal factor is the motivation to lead, which involves an individual's intrinsic and extrinsic drive to assume leadership roles and influence others (Chan & Drasgow, 2021). Motivation to lead can stem from a desire to make a difference, a sense of responsibility, or the pursuit of organizational success. It also affects how individuals respond to leadership development opportunities and whether they seek out or avoid leadership responsibilities. Past experiences also contribute significantly to leadership readiness. Experiences such as handling team conflicts, managing projects, or facing ethical dilemmas help to build the cognitive and emotional skills necessary for leadership. These experiences provide a foundation for learning from successes and failures and developing a nuanced understanding of leadership in practice (Day, Fleenor, Atwater, Sturm, & McKee, 2021).

Concept of Competitive advantage

Competitive advantage is gained when a firm adds value for customers; it is not exclusively about production cost reduction. It entails providing market solutions that competitors cannot deliver, and it must accomplish a firm's position or its market leadership. Firms can thus take advantage of their capabilities and competencies to promote business growth and gain competitive advantages (1985)

Porter (1985) The first refers to the lower production cost achieved by the firm, which provides greater productivity by marketing its product more effectively and choosing more competitive prices. The second refers to the differentiation of products and services, the ability to offer the customer a superior final value product or service in terms of product quality, specific features, and/or support services. According to Porter (1985) these sources are embedded in the competitive process, directly implying the creation of competitive advantages and their long-term sustainability.

However, Barney (2001) and Rua (2019) mentions that the firm must consider the available resources that can be the differential for the construction and consolidation of the market. Thus, a competitive advantage is accomplished when an organizational strategy can create innovative products for the customer. Therefore, the most significant opportunities for value creation are being seized by retail chains; these are decisive for improving the quality of the firm's products and services and maintaining competitive advantage (Bilińska-Reformat, Kucharska; Twardzik, and Dolega, 2019). For Simão and Franco (2018), the difference between the firm's product or service with its competitors should be durably grounded in the market. Analyzing the impact of different sources of knowledge (internal and external) for organizational innovation adoption and decision making can stimulate the introduction of new management practices because external sources are the main drivers for innovative ideas

.Measures of Competitive advantage

Customer Satisfaction

Numerous happy clients are a necessary prerequisite for the survival of many businesses in the market. Customers are the primary driver of a company's existence and market growth. Therefore, it follows that businesses who wish to compete must provide their clients useful and

distinctive conditions that meet their demands. This pleasure covers not only the emotions experienced throughout the buying process but also the environment both before and after the actual purchase. If a business becomes closer to its customers, it may more easily fulfill their requirements and wants over time¹. Therefore, continuing to meet customer expectations is essential for the company's long-term success.² . Customer delight and customer satisfaction are often linked. Products and services that provide clients pleasure give them the desired value, at least to a sufficient extent. According to ISO 10004: "consumer satisfaction is a judgment and an opinion conveyed by the consumer.

The degree of satisfaction indicates the discrepancy between the customer's impression of the supplied goods and their expectations for it. Many variables, including economic ones like income, price, savings, loans, and the influence of marketing tools, as well as noneconomic ones like demographic, sociological, and psychological ones, have an impact on every choice that a consumer makes.⁴ Recognizing and meeting the requirements, expectations, preferences, and behaviors of customers is difficult, and even understanding these things does not ensure success in the market. This is due to the irrational nature of customer behavior. Customers who buy a certain item often have predetermined standards for that commodity's quality, function, or usage. They don't really buy the goods; instead, they pay for the value or what they anticipate from the product. Expectations vary in breadth and may sometimes be either too optimistic or surprisingly pessimistic. Because of this, beginning and defining the customer's unique demands comes before the consumer makes a choice.

One of the most important instruments for a successful company has been customer happiness. According to Fornell et al. (1996), customer satisfaction is an assessment of a product or service based on the total number of purchases and consuming experiences the customer has had with it over time. Customer satisfaction goes hand in hand with marketing, determining the expectations of the consumer on how the businesses are facilitating the products and services. Therefore, a key result is actionable knowledge on how to increase customer satisfaction (Oliver, 1999). Customer retention, product repurchase, and customer happiness are all critical elements of a corporate strategy. Companies should market concepts and approaches after completing all required paperwork in order to increase client satisfaction. Customers, for instance, will purchase a vehicle after giving it a deeper inspection to see things like how the engine is doing, what type

it is, how many miles it has covered, and whether or not it has any cracks. As a result, people do not experience disappointment after buying it. Customers could assume that the automobile is precisely like what they see in the photographs or at the exhibition if the firm simply employs its sell and build technique, and if anything is wrong afterwards, the company might get complaints.

Cost leadership

Cost leadership describe an organizational competitive strategy aimed at achieving lowest cost production while optimizing production efficiency, controlling overhead expenses, and leveraging the experience curve, which indicates that costs per unit decrease as total output increases. . This strategy is more suitable for market share leader as it involves heavy financial and production cost. The strategy is achieved by excelling at: Cost reduction and efficiencies in designing, producing and marketing comparable products than competitors, maximizing economies of scale, implementing cost cutting technologies, and emphasizing cost decrease especially efficient cost management of overheads and administrative expenses; forestalling of auxiliary consumer accounts and minimizing expenditure in sections reminiscent of research and development (R&D) and sales force. A low-cost leader is able to use its cost advantage to charge lesser prices or enjoy superior profit margins; and thus, the firm can reasonably compete in situations of price wars and attack rivals on price to gain substantial share of the available market. Firms seeking low-cost leadership monitor any low-cost technology that may be developed by a competitor (Porter, 2004).

Cost leadership as a strategy enables a firm to be a low-cost producer and as such, its profits exceed those of competitors owing to reduced costs of production as well as inherent economies of scale. The strategy manifests itself within an organization vide the invaluable experience gained sustained investment in production, preservation, and keen supervision of costs of operation with a view to enhancing firm performance. Organizations are, therefore, able to comparative advantage through growing of overall turnover and profitability (Pearce and Robinson, 2014). Organisations that seek after cost leadership need to constantly benchmark their cost operations against those of competing firms with the sole objective of gauging their relative cost and profitability standing in a seemingly business-related Centre. Such firms often achieve positions of comfort by putting great emphasis on dynamic cost control measures, efficient record keeping, Research and Development (R&D) and publicity and marketing related campaigns (Porter, 2004).

Theoretical framework of the study

This study is premised on the assumptions of Lewin's change model (1940) popularly known as the unfreeze- change-refreeze model. The model holds the assumption that organizations and people resist change unless certain psychological and structural conditions are met.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey design with a population of 141 top level managers drawn across 34 hotels in Port Harcourt. The structure questionnaire was used in collecting data from respondents across the 34 hostels in Rivers state, we adopted the use of the spearman rank correlation statistical tool in testing the relationship between the dimensions of the predictor variable and the measures of criterion variable..

Table 4.17: Correlation Matrix for Individual readiness and competitive advantage

			Individual readiness	Customer satisfaction	Cost leadership
Spearman' s rho	Individual readiness	Correlation	1.000	.263*	.253
		Coefficient			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.043	.032
		N	141	141	141
	Customer satisfaction	Correlation	.263*	1.000	.802**
		Coefficient			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.043	.	.000
		N	141	141	141
	Cost leadership	Correlation	.253	.802**	1.000
Coefficient					
Sig. (2-tailed)		.052	.000	.	

	N	141	141	141
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*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results in the above table indicate that there is a significant relationship between individual readiness and customer satisfaction, were as we found out that there is no significant relationship between individual readiness and financial stability as well as growth. Individual readiness is significantly correlated to customer satisfaction ($r = 0.263$, $p = 0.043 < 0.05$). There is significant relationship between individual readiness and cost leadership ($r = .253$, $p = 0.032, < 0.05$);

Correlation Matrix for leadership readiness and Competitive advantage

			Leadership readiness	Customer satisfaction	Cost leadership
Spearman's rho	Leadership readiness	Correlation	1.000	.514**	.437**
		Coefficient			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
		N	141	141	141
	Customer satisfaction	Correlation	.514**	1.000	.802**
		Coefficient			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		N	141	141	141
	Cost leadership	Correlation	.437**	.802**	1.000
		Coefficient			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
		N	141	141	141

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results in table above indicate that there is a significant relationship between leadership readiness and competitive advantage of hospitality firms. This is observed in our output: leadership change readiness impacts customer satisfaction ($r = 0.514$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Leadership readiness is significantly correlated to cost leadership ($r = .437$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

Discussion of findings .

Our findings revealed individual readiness as a strong predictor of competitive advantage of hospitality firms, this is because Organizations change and act through their members, and successful change will persist over the long term only when individuals alter their on-the-job behaviors in appropriate ways (George & Jones, 2021). Many change efforts fail because change leaders often underestimate the central role individuals play in the change process. To support the idea, these researchers have empirically demonstrated that individuals are not passive recipients of organizational change but actors who actively interpret and respond to what is happening in their environments (Greenhalgh et al., 2004; Hall & Hord, 1987; Isabella, 1990; Lowstedt, 1993). Furthermore, some recent research studies also have shown that employees' attitudes toward organizational change influence their behavioral support for a change such that those who had positive attitudes toward organizational change were more likely to change their behavior and champion the change initiatives (e.g., Jones, Jimmieson, & Griffiths, 2005; J. P. Meyer, Srinivas, Lal, & Topolnytsky, 2007).

Considering organizations as a collection of continuously evolving human action, it is no exaggeration to say that individual change readiness is a predictor of organizationl survival and competitive advantage (Tsoukas & Chia, 2022). Organizations are in a continuous state of change and, in order to survive, individuals within the organization must develop the ability to continuously change themselves incrementally and, in many cases, in a fundamental manner (Burnes, 2014). Individuals thus, must continually change with new initiatives introduced by their organizational leaders . However, in reality, many change efforts do not result in their intended aims and do not foster sustained change. Specifically, researchers like Beer and Nohria (2020) estimated that about two-thirds of change projects fail, and Burnes (2014) suggested that the failure rate may be even higher.

Change ready employees learn new apps quickly, use telematics properly, and close delivery loops in real time. This increases drop density, reduces empty miles and fuel wastage, and improves on-time delivery—key to winning and keeping enterprise accounts. In same vein supervisors who are change ready follow new so the firm can add volume without service collapse. Change readiness is crucial for the long-term success of any organization. Change is inevitable, irrespective of its nature whether implementing new technology, restructuring the business, or launching a new product hence organizations must stay ready to changes at all times.

Leadership change readiness and competitive advantage.

The result of the Spearman Rank Order Correlation in our second output shows the presence of a significant association between leadership readiness and competitive advantage. In our study we observed that leaders in most of the hospitality firms in Rivers state are overly change ready, this defines the degree to which senior leaders are aligned, willing and able to mobilize people and resources to execute a change. Change readiness blends two things: a shared commitment to the change and a shared belief that the organization can actually carry it out. When these are high, organizations start faster, persist through obstacles and coordinate better

Leadership readiness to change plays a critical role in shaping the strategic growth of organisations. When leaders demonstrate openness, adaptability, and commitment to transformation, they create a culture that supports innovation and long-term competitiveness (Vakola, 2016). Change-ready leaders are able to anticipate external pressures such as market shifts, technological disruptions, and regulatory demands, aligning strategic objectives with new realities (Armenakis & Harris, 2009). A leader's readiness to change also strengthens employee engagement and reduces resistance, as staff are more likely to trust and follow leaders who model flexibility and resilience (Kotter, 2012). This readiness ensures smoother implementation of new strategies, reduces risks of failure, and accelerates growth trajectories. For instance, research highlights that leadership readiness enhances strategic agility, enabling firms to reallocate resources quickly and exploit emerging opportunities (Judge & Douglas, 2009).

Successful change initiatives require strong leadership and guidance. When leaders actively support and promote change, employees are much more likely to prioritize it and understand its

importance. Leadership is crucial in setting the tone for change by providing direction, resources, and alignment with the organization's vision and goals. Without strong leadership, employees may feel uncertain and unsupported, leading to resistance and disengagement. To prevent this, leaders must communicate the vision, provide guidance and resources, and involve employees in the change process. By demonstrating their support for the change initiative, leaders can build momentum, create buy-in, and increase the likelihood of successful implementation.

Furthermore, leadership readiness fosters a learning-oriented environment where experimentation and innovation are encouraged. This adaptability not only improves operational efficiency but also secures long-term sustainability by positioning the organisation to respond proactively to uncertainty (Higgs & Rowland, 2011). Ultimately, leaders who are psychologically and strategically prepared for change contribute directly to organisational resilience, competitiveness, and sustainable strategic growth.

Many managers rightfully worry about developing and implementing change initiatives. If people do not want to change, for whatever reason, any initiative will likely fail. But we also know that if the people involved can co-create the foundation for change and believe they can implement what needs to be done, they are more likely to cooperate, contribute, collaborate, and deal with any emerging problems along the way. The result is a more effective, efficient, and successful change initiative (Kotter, 2017). We call this phenomenon readiness for change.

For most hospitality firms, leadership change readiness is therefore not a soft factor at the margins. It is a strategic asset that links the company's growth thesis to execution. The findings of our study also affirms the assertion of Vakola, (2016) which stated that leadership readiness to change plays a critical role in shaping the strategic growth of organizations. When leaders demonstrate openness, adaptability, and commitment to transformation, they create a culture that supports innovation and long-term competitiveness. Change-ready leaders are able to anticipate external pressures such as market shifts, technological disruptions, and regulatory demands, aligning strategic objectives with new realities (Armenakis & Harris, 2009).

Conclusions

We therefore make the following conclusions based on our findings that organizational change readiness predict the competitive advantage of hospitality firms in Rivers state..

Recommendations

On the basis of conclusions arrived in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Organizations should encourage individual employees on continuous learning and adaptability, this is because individual employees who are mentally and emotionally ready for change are more likely to embrace innovation, new technologies and evolving business models and thereby enhancing competitive advantage of the firm.
1. Leaders in the organisation should build and empower change agents across all levels of the organization through training and mentorship, they themselves should spare head the change process

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